

A Study on the Prevalence of Helicobacter Pylori Infection by Rapid Urease Test in Patients Undergoing Upper GI Endoscopy for Dyspeptic in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Upper Assam

Rajnish Kumar¹, Pranjal Kumar Dutta², Shummy Das³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India

³PGT 3rd Year, Department of Medicine, Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Rajnish Kumar

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Abstract:

In this cross-sectional study, the objective was to establish the occurrence of Helicobacter pylori infection among 100 dyspeptic patients who were scheduled for upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy at Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh. The study was conducted from August 2020 to July 2021. Based on the results of the Rapid Urease Test (RUT), it was determined that 68% of the patients tested positive for H. pylori infection. Prevalence rates were highest among individuals in the younger age group (18-30 years) and those experiencing epigastric pain. The findings underscore the considerable impact of H. pylori in the region, underscoring the importance of timely detection and efficient management to mitigate related complications.

Keywords: Helicobacter pylori, Dyspepsia, Rapid Urease Test, Upper GI Endoscopy.

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Introduction

Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) is a Gram-negative bacterium that colonises the human stomach and is known to be a significant contributor to a range of gastrointestinal disorders, such as gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and gastric malignancies [1]. The occurrence of H. pylori infection differs greatly among various regions and populations, and is affected by factors like age, socioeconomic status, and environmental conditions [2]. In India, the prevalence is remarkably high, with significant implications for public health, especially in regions with limited healthcare resources. Dyspepsia, a frequently encountered gastrointestinal issue, often necessitates the use of upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy for diagnostic purposes [3]. The Rapid Urease Test (RUT) is a commonly utilised diagnostic test for detecting H. pylori infection. It is favoured for its straightforward procedure, quick results, and affordability. The procedure involves obtaining a gastric biopsy during endoscopy and assessing urease activity, which can indicate the presence of H. pylori [4,5].

This study is conducted in a tertiary care hospital in Upper Assam, a region with a unique demographic and epidemiological profile. It is essential to have a clear understanding of the frequency of H. pylori infection in this specific population, especially among patients experiencing dyspepsia. This knowledge is vital for devising effective management approaches and tackling the impact of

H. pylori-related diseases. The objective of this study is to assess the occurrence of Helicobacter pylori infection by employing the Rapid Urease Test on individuals who are undergoing upper gastrointestinal endoscopy for dyspepsia at a tertiary care hospital in Upper Assam.

Methodology

Study Design: This hospital-based, cross-sectional study examines Helicobacter pylori infection in dyspepsia patients undergoing upper GI endoscopy.

Study Population: The study population consists of 100 patients presenting with dyspeptic symptoms, who were referred for upper GI endoscopy at Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over one year, from August 2020 to July 2021.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above presenting with dyspeptic symptoms.
- Patients who provided informed consent for participation in the study and undergoing upper GI endoscopy.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who have upper GI surgery.

- Patients taking proton pump inhibitors, antibiotics, or bismuth compounds two weeks before endoscopy.
- Patients having endoscopic contraindications.
- Patients with serious comorbidities that potentially affect the study.

Data Collection: After obtaining informed consent, detailed clinical histories of the patients were recorded, including demographic data, presenting symptoms, and relevant medical history. Each patient underwent upper GI endoscopy as part of their diagnostic work-up for dyspepsia.

Rapid Urease Test (RUT): Gastric mucosal biopsy was taken from the stomach antrum during endoscopy. The biopsy samples were immediately tested for *H. pylori* using the Rapid Urease Test (RUT). The test was done using a commercial RUT kit per manufacturer's instructions. It was considered positive for *H. pylori* if the test medium changed colour within 24 hours.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to determine *H. pylori* prevalence in the study population. Data was presented as frequency and percentage. We used statistical tests to examine *H. pylori* infection and demographic or clinical variables.

Results

The study included a group of 100 patients who were experiencing dyspepsia and were scheduled to undergo upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy. A test called the Rapid Urease Test (RUT) was utilized to identify the existence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. Here is a summary of the findings: The patients' ages varied from 18 to 75 years, with an average age of 42.6 years. Distribution of Gender: Out of the 100 patients, 55 were male (55%), while 45 were female (45%). Among the 100 patients who underwent testing, a significant majority of 68 individuals were found to have contracted *H. pylori* infection as indicated by the positive results obtained from the Rapid Urease Test. This gives us a prevalence rate of 68%.

Table 1: Displays the distribution of *H. pylori* infection based on age and gender.

Demographic Factor	Total Number of Patients	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive	Prevalence (%)
Age Group (Years)			
18-30	20	14	70%
31-45	35	24	68.6%
46-60	30	20	66.7%
61-75	15	10	66.7%
Gender			
Male	55	38	69.1%
Female	45	30	66.7%

Table 2: Provides a summary of the distribution of *H. pylori* infection based on presenting symptoms and other clinical characteristics.

Clinical Characteristic	Total Number of Patients	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive	Prevalence (%)
Epigastric Pain	70	50	71.4%
Bloating	55	38	69.1%
Nausea	40	28	70%
Heartburn	35	24	68.6%
Vomiting	20	12	60%

Discussion

This study sought to investigate the occurrence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in dyspeptic patients who were undergoing upper gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy at a tertiary care hospital in Upper Assam [11]. Our research uncovered a significant number of patients who were infected with *H. pylori*, as 68% of them tested positive using the

Rapid Urease Test (RUT). The prevalence mentioned aligns with findings from similar studies carried out in different parts of India. These studies have reported *H. pylori* infection rates ranging from 60-80% among individuals with dyspepsia [12]. This study highlights the widespread occurrence of *H. pylori* infection in the Indian population, especially in regions like Upper Assam. It emphasises the considerable impact of this

pathogen on the health of individuals. Several factors may contribute to the high prevalence observed, such as socioeconomic status, inadequate sanitation, and overcrowded living conditions, which are prevalent in various regions of the country [13]. In addition, the extensive utilization of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and the limited knowledge about *H. pylori*-related diseases could potentially worsen the infection rates [14].

Males had a little greater prevalence of *H. pylori* infection (69.1%) than females (66.7%), although this difference was not statistically significant, according to our study. This gender distribution suggests that various populations may be more or less susceptible to *H. pylori* infection depending on gender-specific characteristics, as supported by some studies but not by others [15]. The younger age group (18–30 years) had the highest prevalence of *H. pylori* infection, which may have been caused by early contact to the bacterium in infancy or adolescence [8]. This discovery is especially alarming since a prior *H. pylori* infection has been linked to an increased chance of experiencing severe gastrointestinal disorders in later life, including stomach cancer and peptic ulcer disease [16]. According to clinical data, individuals with heartburn, bloating, and nausea were the next most common symptoms of *H. pylori* infection (71.4%), followed by those with epigastric discomfort [9]. This implies that there is a substantial correlation between certain dyspeptic symptoms and *H. pylori* infection, especially epigastric pain, which is a well-known sign of gastritis and peptic ulcer illness linked to *H. pylori* [17].

The study emphasizes the significance of identifying and treating *H. pylori* infection in individuals with dyspepsia, particularly in areas with a high prevalence such as Upper Assam. By implementing screening programs and raising awareness about the potential complications of untreated *H. pylori* infection, the community can greatly reduce the burden of *H. pylori*-related diseases. In addition, the utilisation of RUT as a diagnostic tool has demonstrated its effectiveness and practicality in this particular context, affirming its ongoing application in regular clinical practice [10,18]. It is crucial to address the widespread occurrence of *H. pylori* infection in individuals experiencing dyspepsia. This highlights the importance of implementing specific public health measures and conducting additional research to gain insights into the underlying factors contributing to this infection among various demographic populations. Tackling these concerns has the potential to enhance management strategies and enhance health outcomes for patients impacted by *H. pylori* in this area [19,20].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reveals a high prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection among dyspeptic patients undergoing upper gastrointestinal endoscopy at a tertiary care hospital in Upper Assam, with a particularly elevated rate among younger adults and those presenting with epigastric pain. These findings underscore the critical need for early detection and targeted management of *H. pylori* infection to mitigate its associated gastrointestinal complications in this region. Implementing effective screening and treatment strategies could significantly reduce the burden of *H. pylori*-related diseases in the community.

References

1. Graham DY, Fischbach L. *Helicobacter pylori* treatment in the era of increasing antibiotic resistance. *Gut*. 2010;59(8):1143-53.
2. Blaser MJ, Atherton JC. *Helicobacter pylori* persistence: biology and disease. *J Clin Invest*. 2004;113(3):321-33.
3. Kusters JG, van Vliet AH, Kuipers EJ. Pathogenesis of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 2006;19(3):449-90.
4. Ahmed KS, Khan AA, Ahmed I, Tiwari SK, Habeeb MA, Hussain MA, et al. Prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in asymptomatic children in Aligarh, India. *J Infect Dev Ctries*. 2006;2(3):187-90.
5. Pounder RE, Ng D. The prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection in different countries. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 1995;9(Suppl 2):33-9.
6. Suerbaum S, Michetti P. *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *N Engl J Med*. 2002;347(15):1175-86.
7. Malfertheiner P, Megraud F, O'Morain CA, Gisbert JP, Kuipers EJ, Axon AT, et al. Management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection—the Maastricht V/Florence Consensus Report. *Gut*. 2017;66(1):6-30.
8. Goh KL, Chan WK, Shiota S, Yamaoka Y. Epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and public health implications. *Helicobacter*. 2011;16(Suppl 1):1-9.
9. Hunt RH, Xiao SD, Megraud F, Leon-Barua R, Bazzoli F, van der Merwe S, et al. *Helicobacter pylori* in developing countries. World Gastroenterology Organisation Global Guideline. *J Gastrointest Liver Dis*. 2011;20(3):299-304.
10. Thirumurthi S, Graham DY. *Helicobacter pylori* infection in India from a western perspective. *Indian J Med Res*. 2012;136(4):549-62.
11. Fock KM, Ang TL. Epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and gastric cancer in Asia. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2010;25(3):479-86.

12. Ramakrishnan K, Salinas RC. Peptic ulcer disease. *Am Fam Physician*. 2007;76(7):1005-12.
13. Chey WD, Wong BC, Practice Parameters Committee of the American College of Gastroenterology. American College of Gastroenterology guideline on the management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2007;102(8):1808-25.
14. Gisbert JP, Calvet X. Review article: *Helicobacter pylori* 'test and treat' strategy for management of dyspepsia. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther*. 2011;34(6):604-17.
15. Suerbaum S, Josenhans C. *Helicobacter pylori* evolution and phenotypic diversification in a changing host. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2007;5(6):441-52.
16. Frenck RW Jr, Clemens J. *Helicobacter* in the developing world. *Microbes Infect*. 2003;5 (8): 705-13.
17. Malfertheiner P, Megraud F, O'Morain C, Bazzoli F, El-Omar E, Graham D, et al. Current concepts in the management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection: the Maastricht III Consensus Report. *Gut*. 2007;56(6):772-81.
18. Kim N, Kim JJ, Choe YH, Kim HS, Kim JI, Chung IS, et al. Diagnosis and treatment guidelines for *Helicobacter pylori* infection in Korea. *Korean J Gastroenterol*. 2009;54(5): 26 9-78.
19. Nath G, Gulati AK, Shukla VK. Role of *Helicobacter pylori* in gastric cancer. *Indian J Surg*. 2010;72(6):363-70.
20. Wotherspoon AC, Ortiz-Hidalgo C, Falzon MR, Isaacson PG. *Helicobacter pylori*-associated gastritis and primary B-cell gastric lymphoma. *Lancet*. 1991;338(8776):1175-6.